



Fig. 4. The transmission spectra of glass plates with precipitated metal particles after exposure of 5 plasma pulses to foils: W, Ti (argon plasma); V (nitrogen plasma). 1 – original glass; 2 – glass with V particles; 3 – W; and 4 – Ti. The thickness of the foil (mm) is as follows: V – 0.16, W – 0.6, and Ti – 0.9.